

1540 cm^{-1} move to higher frequencies in the complex and appear at 1590, 1580 (sh) and 1565 cm^{-1} , respectively. The bands at 1449 and 1408 cm^{-1} move to 1480 and 1470 cm^{-1} , and a new band at 1330 cm^{-1} (absent in free base) is attributed to chelation as suggested earlier⁶. Similarly, the absorptions at 1608, 1578 and 1415 cm^{-1} in uncomplexed phen show a positive shift to 1620, 1590 and 1430 cm^{-1} in the adduct and a new band at 1140 cm^{-1} (absent in pure ligand) is an evidence of chelation⁶. $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnN}_3\cdot\text{TMEN}$ shows a positive shift of νCN mode by $\approx 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showing $\text{M}\leftarrow\text{N}$ bonding. The presence of coordinated base in complexes of Ph_3SnN_3 with en, pn and TMP is indicated by the distinct negative shift in $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ absorptions as compared to those in corresponding free bases⁷.

O donor complexes containing ($X=O$) ($X=C, N, P, S$): The νCO at 1666 cm^{-1} in the free anti-pyrene undergoes a distinct negative shift and appears at 1610 and 1590 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating coordination through the carbonyl oxygen⁸. The ir spectra of uncomplexed DMA and DMF show intense absorptions at 1633 and 1670 cm^{-1} , respectively assigned to νCO^τ .

In the ir spectrum of free Eu and 1-Me-2-pyr the νCO appears at 1680 cm^{-1} and 1655 cm^{-1} and shows a negative shift to 1650 cm^{-1} and 1620 cm^{-1} in their respective adducts, indicating oxygen coordination⁷.

A comparison of the ir spectra of all the azido complexes of N-oxide ligands with free bases (viz., LutO, 2-, 3-, 4-picO and PyO) reveals a large shift of νNO band to lower frequency, as the ir spectra of the adducts exhibit νNO at 1215, 1190, 1150, 1220 and 1210 cm^{-1} respectively as compared to its position at 1246, 1250, 1275, 1250 and 1250 cm^{-1} in the free bases. This indicates oxygen coordination in all the compounds⁹.

In the ir spectra of HMPA and Ph_3PO , the νPO occurs at 1218 and 1195 cm^{-1} and undergoes a large negative shift to 1140, 1130 cm^{-1} and 1150, 1120 cm^{-1} in their adducts, respectively indicating $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bonding in the compounds¹⁰.

In sulphoxide complexes, coordination through the oxygen atom is indicated by the lowering of the $\nu\text{S}=\text{O}$ mode of absorption and a positive shift of the asymmetric $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ mode¹¹.

The coordination site in Ph_3PS is the sulphur atom as is evident from the negative shift of νPS from 637 cm^{-1} in the free ligand¹² to 610 cm^{-1} in the adducts.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for facilities for ir and elemental analyses and the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of them (P.C.K.).

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Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with Some Anionic Schiff's Bases Derived from Furan-2-Carbaldehyde and Some Amino Acids

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Manuscript received 30 November 1981, revised 4 August 1982,
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ALTHOUGH the Schiff bases derived from a variety of aldehydes and amines have been studied extensively as nitrogen donors, the compounds of the heterocyclic aldehydes have been comparatively little investigated so far. The present paper records the synthesis and characterisation of some such complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) derived from furan-2-carbaldehyde and three amino acids.

The specific Schiff bases used are furfural-glycine, furfural- α -alanine and furfural- α -valine which have been obtained in solution by stirring one equivalent of the aldehyde with one equivalent of corresponding amino acid at room temperature in methanol for 6 hr. The reaction with the metal salts has been done *in situ* for which the metal salt in methanol was added to the above solution and further stirred for 10 hr. The solid complex separated was filtered, dried and analysed (Table 1). The anion of the ligand may be represented by Structure I.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	C	H	N	
1.	[Cu(C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	18.20 (17.30)	46.02 (45.71)	3.78 (3.289)	15.60 (15.23)	1.90
2.	[Ni(C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	15.1 (16.2)	46.95 (46.32)	3.70 (3.33)	15.85 (15.44)	3.25
3.	[Co(C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	15.3 (16.2)	46.10 (46.30)	3.10 (3.33)	15.95 (15.43)	5.12
4.	[Cu(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	17.0 (16.05)	49.05 (48.54)	4.18 (4.07)	14.70 (14.15)	2.02
5.	[Ni(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	14.03 (15.01)	48.95 (49.14)	3.98 (4.12)	14.05 (14.33)	3.08
6.	[Co(C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂]	15.9 (15.0)	49.80 (49.12)	4.90 (4.12)	14.70 (14.32)	5.45
7.	[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]	13.2 (14.057)	52.98 (53.14)	5.68 (5.35)	13.00 (12.39)	1.98
8.	[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]	12.5 (13.13)	53.05 (53.72)	5.00 (5.41)	13.08 (12.53)	3.45
9.	[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]	13.9 (13.16)	53.12 (53.69)	5.08 (5.41)	12.10 (12.52)	5.08

L (anionic form) I

R = H, CH₃, CH(OH)₂,
L = C₇H₈O₂N; C₈H₈O₂N; C₁₀H₁₁O₂N.

The carboxylic group of the acid adjacent to the azomethine group is expected to be deprotonated on treatment with the metal salts, and hence the Schiff bases would form complexes in the anionic form and will act as uninegative, tridentate ligands having one azomethine, one COO⁻ and one furfural ring oxygen as the donor. Their complexes with all the three metals i.e. Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) have been prepared and their structures have been resolved on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral data.

The metals have been estimated by known methods, while C, H and N have been estimated microanalytically (Table 1). The molar conductances of the complexes in methanol are around 7.00 mho, indicative of their neutral nature. Their formulae are thus [M(L)₂]. The ligands appear to be tridentate for Ni(II) and Co(II) giving hexacoordinated complexes while for Cu(II) it is proposed that the COO⁻ group of the ligand is not coordinating but simply neutralising the charge on the metal and thus the ligands function as bidentate to copper. This is supported by the infrared spectra of free and coordinated ligands.

The azomethine stretch in free ligands occurs around 1660 cm⁻¹, which may shift either to higher or to lower wave numbers on coordination, depending upon various factors as reported^{3,8}. In the present complexes the νCN occurs at 1600 cm⁻¹ and

hence it is suggested that coordination causes a weakening of >C=N— bond due to both, σ and π interactions occurring simultaneously which decrease the total electron density of ligand.

For the carboxylate ion, the information regarding coordination is drawn from the positions of asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ frequencies, which occur at 1640 and 1550 cm⁻¹ in free ligands. The formation of M—O bond drains the electrons from the COO⁻ group and decreases the C—O bond order and frequency. In Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes these frequencies occur at 1605 and 1488 cm⁻¹ clearly indicating coordination, while in the Cu(II) complexes these occur at 1662 and 1545 cm⁻¹. Hence it is concluded that COO⁻ group is not coordinating⁴⁻⁶. The presence of a very sharp band around 500 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes shows the formation of another M—O bond involving furan ring oxygen⁷⁻¹⁰. The detailed structure of complexes has been established by magnetic and electronic structural data as follows.

All the three copper(II) complexes possess μ_{eff} values of 1.90-2.20 B.M. indicating the presence of a single unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra these show a single broad band in the region 12.00-17.00 kK accompanied by 8 weak shoulders on either side. These are assigned as ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} (16.00 kK), ²B_{1g} → ²E_g (22.00 kK) and ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} (10.00 kK). This is consistent with square planar environment for copper¹¹⁻¹³.

The nickel(II) complexes are also paramagnetic with μ_{eff} in the range 3.02-3.50 B.M. corresponding to spin free octahedral configuration. In confirmation of this, three bands are seen in the spectra at 25.00, 16.60 and 11.50 kK corresponding to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P)(ν₃), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F)(ν₂) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F)(ν₁) transitions, respectively as found for other octahedral complexes. The values of Dq, B, β and the ratio ν₃/ν₁ are around 960 cm⁻¹, 1000 cm⁻¹,

0.92 and 1.68 and these also support the Oh symmetry of the complexes^{1,4,15}.

The cobalt(II) complexes are also paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values of 5.12 B.M. Since these values may correspond to a tetrahedral or octahedral configuration, the μ_{eff} at two low temperatures was also determined and given below.

Complex	303K	257K	143K
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	5.12 B.M.	4.98 B.M.	4.96 B.M.
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	5.46 B.M.	5.00 B.M.	5.14 B.M.
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N})_2]$	5.20 B.M.	5.18 B.M.	5.32 B.M.

It is clear that the values are independent of temperature and hence correspond to an octahedral geometry with T ground state. In the tetrahedral structures with A ground term, on the other hand, the values increase considerably with temperature. In the spectra also three sharp bands are seen clearly at 22,00, 16,00 and 7.57 kK assigned as ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{P})(\nu_3)$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{1g}(\text{F})(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})(\nu_1)$ corresponding to octahedral geometry. The ν_3 band is mostly split into two components, one at 22.83 kK and the other at 18.86 kK. The Dq, B and β values are around 757 cm^{-2} , 960 cm^{-1} and 0.98 and correspond to the assigned geometry^{16,17}.

This discussion clearly indicates that the Schiff bases used in the study function as strong ligands and the β values indicate the presence of large covalent character on complexes. The splitting of ν_2 band in Ni(II) and ν_3 band in Co(II) complexes is due to the lowering of symmetry upon coordination.

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Some Reactions of 8-Quinolinol-N-oxide with Bis(η^5 -Cyclopentadienyl)titanium Dichloride

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Manuscript received 31 October 1981, revised 11 August 1982, accepted 28 December 1982

ANDRAE used sodamide in boiling benzene or toluene as a suitable condensing base for the preparation of phenoxy derivatives of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride¹. Survey of literature indicates that the reaction of 8-quinolinol with (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂ has been reported² but there is no mention of the reaction of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide with (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂. This note deals with the preparation of N-oxido-8-quinolinolates of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride.

Experimental

The preparations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Benzene, toluene, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran were purified and dried. Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride³ and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide⁴ were prepared by the reported methods. Titanium was estimated gravimetrically, chlorine by Volhards' method and carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen by the microcombustion procedure.

NMR spectrum was recorded in CDCl₃ on Perkin-Elmer R-32. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer Infracord model-621 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets.

Preparation of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)-N-oxido-8-quinolinolato titanium chloride, (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂-(C₉H₈O₂N)TiCl: Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride (0.415 g; 0.0016 mole) and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (0.536 g; 0.0032 mole) were added to a suspension of sodamide (5 g) in toluene (200 ml). The mixture was refluxed with constant stirring for 30 min. The cooled mixture was filtered through a sintered glass funnel (porosity G-4) and the filtrate concentrated to ~ 20 ml and treated with petroleum ether. A slight brown coloured crystalline compound was obtained, which was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. It was soluble in benzene, chloroform, THF, etc., did not melt below 315° and turned dark on heating. (Found: C, 60.5; H, 4.3; N, 3.6; Ti, 12.78, Cl, 9.6. (C₉H₈)₂-(C₉H₈O₂N)TiCl requires C, 61; H, 4.3; N, 3.7; Ti, 12.85; Cl, 9.5%).

Preparation of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)di(N-oxido-8-quinolinolato)titanium, (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂(C₉H₈O₂N)₂Ti: Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride (0.45 g; 0.0016 mole) and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (0.538 g; 0.0032 mole) were dissolved in dry acetonitrile (40 ml) [or benzene (200 ml)]. To this was added 0.34 g (0.0032 mole) of triethylamine with constant shaking. A yellow crystalline compound settled down, which was allowed to stand over night. The